

CHALLENGING ISSUE OF TRIBAL WOMEN EDUCATION IN INDIA

Suman Kumari

Research Scholar, Babasahib Bhimrao Ambedkar University,
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:

The purpose of the paper is to analyze the situation of the tribal women education with literacy rate gross enrolment ratio .dropout rate and check the real condition of tribal women in the India. There are various obstacles along with the path of education of tribal women attempts have also been made to ascertain the measure taken by the government to improve the present status of education. In India, education of tribal women is major preoccupation of both government and civil society because the education is very important instrument for the development of the country. For the development of the society, inclusive progress of all section is required, and for this perspective, it is necessary to bring the tribal women, such as deprived, weaker and marginalized section of society to the forefront, of these human resources of the educational revolution in India. It is important for equal development and overall development of the nation .Provides education, knowledge, and knowledge of self and knowing and removing its problem related to exploitation. This analysis is based on the secondary data of India census 2011. In 1961 the tribal women literacy rate was only 3.16 % which is increased to 49.35 % in 2011. However, even after sixty seven years of independence, the goal of universal education has not yet been achieved. About 10 million children of school going age are not get education due to various reasons.

Key Words: Education, Literacy, Tribe & Poverty

Introduction:

"If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered".

PT. Jawaharlal Nehru

Education is the key to success. The similarly is true for women. Women are the centers of creation in this world. Women do not even know themselves for which they have created. Woman has played a stable and defined role in the society, from daughter, sister, wife and mother. The true evaluation of their contribution to the family, society and the country is scarcely done or counted till date. In this intense changing society and the world, women have to get aware about themselves, responsibilities, and their rights. At present times the role of women is consider in all aspects of social fiber. Many studies in the past have proved that they are playing a creative role in nation-building. Education of women, which is about half of the nation's population, therefore, undoubtedly is the important for developing country like India.

Women are the first teacher of the child in the whole world. Therefore, education of women is certainly considered the most important part of the development of the society. Napoleon was asked once, what was the great need of France. They replied, "progress of the nation is impossible without educated mother .if the women of my country are not educated the about half of the people will be illiterate. Mothers duty does not end with giving birth to many children, In our society has not even seen distinguished. It is quality which is currently needed by society. Therefore, our human community must also understand the need of their education for the improvement of the society. Women education can help solve their problems, such as birth control, drug, poverty, dowry system, bridge burning case, inequality of women in society and child labor etc.

India is home to large variety of indigenous people. Scheduled tribe population represents one of the most economically poor and marginalized community in India. With a population of more than 10.2 million, India has the largest tribal population in the world. It is 8.2 percent of the total population of the country. (India’census, 2011). Most tribal’s people are inhabitant in poor, uneducated and inaccessible forest and mountainous areas. They all lie behind area of life compared to other section of the population .Government of India has started many schemes for the promotion of education and welfare in tribal and in particular. Despite these efforts, Literacy rate there is no improvement. In the case of primitive tribes, it is very poor and among the women, it is very low. Literacy is the key to the socio-economic development of any class or region, and this is why tribal’s communities across India are under differentiation from different types of deprived, such as separation from land and other resources. Especially tribal women they are far the mainstream of national life.

Education of Tribal Women in India:

There are more than 500 tribes as notified under article 342 of the Constitution of India, in various States and Union Territories of the country, the largest number of tribal communities being in the State of Uttar Pradesh. Although Scheduled Tribes are a minority, they are about 8.2 % of the total population of India. About 93% of the tribal people live in rural areas and are engaged in agricultural pursuits. In Ten States like Andhra Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal which together account for more than four-fifths of the total tribal population in India. The trend of the literacy in the tribes of India from 1961 to 2001 was shown on table – 1. The percentage of literacy of tribes was only 8.54 % in 1961 which has increased to 47.10 % in 2001. But female literacy among tribes is only 34.76 % compared to male literacy of 59.17.

Table 1: Literacy Trends for Scheduled Tribes in India from 1961 to 2011(In Percent)

Year	Total	Male	Female
1961	8.53	13.83	3.16
1971	11.30	17.63	4.85
1981	16.35	24.52	8.05
1991	29.60	40.65	18.19
2001	47.10	59.17	34.76
2011	58.96	68.53	49.35

Source: National Commission for SCs & STs, Fifth Report & Census, 2011.

Percentage of Literacy:

Realizing the need to improve the overall status of tribes, their education has emerged at the forefront of recent development efforts. The literacy rates of tribes in rural and urban area in India are shown in table –2 for understanding status of tribal education .Total female literacy of tribes in Uttar Pradesh is very low at 20.70% as compared to male literacy of 48.45%. Bihar has the lowest tribal literacy where as Kerala has highest literacy among the tribes.

Table 2: Rural & Urban Literacy Rates of St in Selected States by Gender

State	Total Male	Total Female	Rural Male	Rural Female	Urban Male	Urban Female
Uttar Pradesh	67.01	43.07	66.02	42.03	74.08	58.00

Bihar	.76	15.54	37.57	13.30	74.18	55.28
Odisha	51.48	23.37	50.35	22.07	69.80	45.77
Madhya Pradesh	53.35	28.44	52.51	27.24	67.47	45.89
Gujarat	59.80	36.02	58.06	34.60	71.01	71.78
Maharashtra	67.02	43.08	64.52	39.88	82.98	64.70
West Bengal	57.38	29.15	56.60	27.88	68.57	48.20
Andhra Pradesh	47.66	26.11	46.09	24.48	66.16	45.99
Rajasthan	62.10	26.16	61.23	25.22	75.74	42.97
Himachal Pradesh	77.71	53.32	77.18	77.18	92.03	81.15
Kerala	70.78	58.11	70.20	57.28	84.96	77.70
India	59.17	34.76	57.39	32.44	77.77	59.87

Source: Annual Report (MHRD). Govt of India.

In spite of education initiatives, there is disparity between the states in the case of tribal literacy rates. Low enrolment coupled with soaring drop-out rates in primary schools increase the problem, which has its origin in a gamut of inter-related cultural and socio-economic variables. Adivasis are associated with a certain stigma and behavior, which can be partially tackled through a change in mindset among non-tribes.

Enrolment Ratio of ST student's Gross enrolment ratio of ST Boys is more than ST girls in all classes. The gross enrolment ratio is higher in class I to V which is 137.2 for ST boys and 136.7 for ST girls but it is only 90.7 and 87 in class VI to VIII. It implies that the tribal enrolment in higher class dropped significantly.

Table 3: Gross enrolment ratio (Ger)

Classes	ST Boys	ST Girls
Classes I- V (6 – 10 years)	137.2	136.7
Classes VI – VIII (11 – 13 years)	90.7	87
Classes IX – X (14 – 15 years)	57.1	49.1
Classes XI- XII (16 - 17 years)	32.7	24.8
Classes I- XII (6 – 17 years)	96.8	92.8

Gender Parity Index reflects the enrolment of girls in school in comparison to boys. The index for ST students is almost same as all categories of students except for class XI to XII. (Table-4)

Table 4: Gender Parity Index in Education

Classes	ST	All
Classes I-V	1.0	1.01
Classes VI- VIII	0.96	0.95
Classes IX- X	0.86	0.88
Classes XI-XII	0.76	0.86
Classes IX-XII	0.82	0.87
Classes I-XII	0.96	0.96

Source: Statistics of School Children, 2010-2011

The dropout ratio of Scheduled tribal girls is higher as compared to all girls in India.

Table 5: School dropout ratio between scheduled tribe boys and girls

Classes	All Boys	All Girls	ST Boys	ST Girls
Classes I-V	28.7	25.1	37.2	33.9
Classes I-VIII	40.3	41.0	54.7	55.4
Classes I-X	50.4	47.9	70.6	71.3

Source: statistics of school education 2010-2011.

Table 6: Percentage of All India girls and ST girls who entered class I and studied up to class XII

Problems and Critical Issues of Tribal Women Education:

There are many critical issues and problems in the field of tribal women education. They are as follows:

Location of the Village: Most of the tribal communities inhabit in the forests in a scattered manner. Therefore, it becomes impossible to open separate schools in each village where the required student's strength is not available. On other hand, tribal habitations remain segregated from each other by some physical barriers like rivers, hills, nalas and forests. So these physical barriers produce an obstacle for the girls of a tribal village to attend the school in a neighboring village. In this situation, parents do not allow their girl child to attend schools. More residential schools should be established in each states and districts and should be extended up to PG level in tribal areas.

Attitude of the Parents: Most of the dropped out girls are living with their family. As per the study signifies, majority of their parents do not have proper education and they are early dropouts. Tribal parents are mostly illiterate. They always show a very indifferent attitude towards the education of their girls. They are interested in providing household responsibilities to their girls a very early stage of their education. "The parents of these girls do not have any relationship with the society outside and are unaware of the importance of education. Teaching such girls is a herculean task.

Negative Attitude towards School Education: Many of the dropouts are having an in favor attitude towards education, they consider education as a boring process. They still are not convinced of the need of education for their livelihood. They are aware of the government's allowances for their education. But a negative attitude towards education makes them stay back in their colony environment than go to school.

Economic Condition: The tribes depend on forests for 8 months and on agriculture for 4 months. The girls of the age group 4 to 6 are found to be helping their parents in collection of forest products. In this situation, parents do not allow to spare their girls or their labor force and allow them to attend schools. When a family not economically secure, prioritizing a girl child education take a backseat. post class V distance from school also tend to increase and parents also feel it unsafe for girl child to travel far.

Appointment of Local Teachers: In the remote tribal areas the teacher absence is a regular occurrence and it largely affects the quality of education. In tribal villages, there is virtually no relation with the teachers of the villagers. Teachers do not get any housing facility in the village, which makes them irregular which inhibits the normal routine of the school. Apart from this, the apathetic attitude of the villagers and the appointment of untrained teachers in tribal areas reduce the values of education.

Lack of Proper Prohibition: Due to bad coordination between the tribal welfare department and the school education department, proper monitoring is inhibited.

Government Policies and Programs for the Education of Tribal Women:

Immediately after independence, systematic and Constitutional for arrangements were made for free and planned efforts in our country, compulsory education for children up to fulfill the national commitment of the age of 14 years. Efforts were made enshrined under article 45 of the through successive five year plans to achieve the target of 100 percent literacy through mandatory and free education for the children up to 14 years. The National Policy on Education 1986 and 1992 are given top preponderance for the accomplishment of goals of Universal Elementary Education (UEE). Multifarious programs and incentives were start for Universalizing and ameliorate the quality of elementary education in India. In spite of, even sixty two years of independence the aim of universal elementary education has not yet been achieved. Nearly 10 million girls of school going ages are not attending elementary schools due to various reasons like poverty, no access to schools. Government of India started a scheme; known as Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) in the year 2001-2002 in partnership with the local self-governments and state Governments. It is an extensive and integrated major program of government of India to achieve universal elementary education cover the whole country in a mission mode. The following are the main objectives of the scheme:

- ✓ Enrolment of all children in school, Education Guarantee Centre, Alternate Schools, Back-to-School camp by 2003;
- ✓ All children complete five years of primary school 2007;
- ✓ All children complete eight years of elementary school by 2010;
- ✓ Focus on elementary education of satisfying quality with significance on education for life;
- ✓ To bridge all gender and social category interval at primary level by 2007 and at elementary education level by 2010;
- ✓ Universal retention by 2010. Other than this, Government of India started many other encouragement schemes to maintain the children in the schools which are given below:(1) Free text books, Stationary, school bags etc; (2) Free uniforms, (3) Mid-day meal scheme, (4) Attendance scholarship for girls etc.

The PESA (The Panchayats Extension to Scheduled Areas) Act, 1996 in fact, has been made it mandatory for the States having scheduled areas to make special provisions for giving broad powers to the tribes on the matters relating to decision-making and development of their community. A centrally-sponsored government program of ashram schools exclusively for ST children from elementary to higher secondary levels

was started in the 1970s. But the poor quality of education in ashram schools, in spite of, has undermined confidence in education as a vehicle for social mobility.

The Janshala Programme is an associate endeavor of the Government of India (GOI) and five UN Agencies –UNDP, UNICEF, UNESCO, ILO and UNFPA –a community based primary education program, goal to make primary education more accessible and efficacious, specially for girls and children in underprivileged communities, marginalized groups, Scheduled Tribes / Scheduled Caste /minorities, children with specific needs.

Suggestions:

Some suggestions for improvement of tribal education are as follows:

The Relevant Study Material in the Local Language: It is strongly suggested for the use of the mother tongue or home language as the medium of instruction in early stages of education. From the perspective of language, it is desirable to be a local teacher from the same tribal communities, all study materials should be supplied in local languages of the tribes.

Literacy Campaign: A proper awareness campaign should be organized to create the awareness about the importance of education. Extensive literacy campaign in the tribal dominated districts may be start work on a priority basis to literate the tribal. More than 50% of dropouts take place in primary school .to dealing with the problems the department has made a team which will go to the tribal areas spreading awareness about various schemes offered by the government to encourage people to send their daughter to school.

Attitude of the Tribal Parents: The attitude of the tribal parents toward education should be improved through proper counseling and guidance.

Stipends and Various Scholarships: Since higher education is less in the tribes, special ST scholarships should be provided to the tribal girls studying higher education, especially in engineering, medical, and other vocational streams.

The Appointment of Local Teachers and Female Teachers: It is suggested to appoint more tribal teachers and female teachers in the tribal areas. Ecological, cultural, psychological characteristics of tribal children should be carefully considered by teachers in tribal areas.

Residential Schools: More residential schools should be established in each states and districts and should be extended to PG level in tribal areas.

Proper Monitoring: High level officials should often examine the working of schools related to teaching methods, working hours and attendance registers

Social Security: Social security of students, especially of adolescent girls is a matter of great concern in residential schools

School Curriculum: The improvement of the School Curriculum Medium and need for excessive improvement through the holiday pattern in tribal dominated areas.

Conclusion:

Education is the only most important instrument by which individuals and society can improve individual endowments, build a level of capacity, overcome obstacles, and expand opportunities for continuous improvement in their welfare. It is not only applicable but also for tribal women. In the context of the education of tribal women, the attitudes of tribal families should be positive and the government should be revised to get a balance between man and women. Various steps should be taken to ensure the success of tribal women in mainstream schools. Teachers should be assign task to motivate parents can enrol their daughters in schools, especially parents, who are hesitant to do so due to unawareness, weak financial status and ignorance. Parents who focus on religious education only for their daughters need motivation and inspiration. Up gradation of girls' schools in remote tribal areas, which are, functioning, The utility of primary and secondary schools will not only support the further education of already enrolled girls but work as a motive for many girls in the areas where they want education. To decrease the impacts of poverty on daughter' education, giving stipend to enrolled girls is a good solution. Since there is not found any strong interruption in Families attitudes for their girls' education, the study encourage the opinion of providing a instrument of quality and easy approachable education for girls in the areas. The steps will support to create an educational environment in the areas as well as broad the mindset of tribal parents.

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